

IMPACT OF MEDIA AND INFORMATION

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Abstract:

Media is acquiring crucial importance at the present era. The Purpose of this study was to examine Social Media use among users and how it affects communication with others. The news and information's are reaching the people faster and more efficiently. At the same time merely little fake news is also created by the media. Because, the necessary aims of the media are earning money by the way of attracting public. This study is based on scientific observations and researched on the literature of local media outlets. Aim of this study is discussed with different perspective to contribution of local media organs to political, cultural and social structure.

Key Words: Social media, Media information & Internet

Introduction:

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that 'Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers. 'In particular, college students form a large proportion of users on social media networks. In recent years Internet appears to have become an inherent part in human lives, both professional and personal. Thus, media is an institution which informs the society, notify them, enables an individual participate public on public matters and inspects the management on behalf of public. The purpose of this study was to examine how social media affects college student's communication with others and how their own self-concept.

Review of Literature:

Vetrivel and Muthulakshmi 2011 in their article stated that the position of radio publicity is now been taken by the television advertising. A variety of techniques are available on television for the production of commercial messages like live action, paper show, cartons, documentary films and use of music, which can increase the memorability and persuade the audience to buy the product.

Gayatri and Sheweta Gaur, 2012, stated Television advertisements usually play a role in introducing a product, reinforcing the familiarity to the product and also convincing to purchase the product. Advertisements are among the most visible of the marketing strategy and have been the subject of a great deal of attention in the last ten to fifteen years. Advertising today seems to be everywhere and ever present exerting a far reaching influence on the daily lives of people.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know about the overall details of media research.
- ✓ Since this social media phenomenon is continuing to grow at a fast pace, it is important to understand its impact.

Need and Role of Media:

Rummel considered media research as "an endeavour to discover, develop and verify knowledge". Its main aim is the discovery of the truth. Using social media sites helped improve the quality of relationships between users & to know about the details of using media users. This field of study is important because sociability is an underlying theme in using forms of social media.

Scope of Media:

The target audience by the way of communication is clearly identified. The media can cover and justify the subject correctly. Print media is the oldest form of media. Print media is published daily or weekly or monthly or quarterly. Nowadays media plays a vital role in economy.

Importance of Media:

- ✓ To collect the information that media, practitioners and professionals need to know to do their jobs more effectively.
- ✓ The media are major sources of modern culture and entertainment.
- ✓ The media are major industries and are inextricably involved in commerce.
- ✓ The media require us to learn and use critical thinking skills.
- ✓ The media explain us to how things work around us.
- ✓ The media are carefully planned, designed and constructed.
- ✓ The media help and define how we communicate with each other.

Swot Analysis:

Strength:

- ✓ If newspaper is wide range of editorial material aimed at a broad audience. The selectivity of newspaper is geographic.
- ✓ The Magazine is in high quality colour reproduction and they are in portable.
- ✓ The Television targets and reaches the correct audience and they reach large number of people.
- ✓ The Radio is portable for all and covers universe and lead time saving also.
- ✓ The Outdoor Advertising reaches the audience 24hours a day and they work well compared with other media.
- ✓ The E-mail communicated from complex information.
- ✓ In Online Advertising the customer can target and buy our selective products and the ability to work easily in any budget.

Weakness:

- ✓ The newspaper is in short life and low quality colour reproduction and they cannot deliver sound and motion always. The magazines cost are comparatively expensive.
- ✓ The Television is long lead time and they are nor portable.
- ✓ The Radio is in short life & No visuals in radio to understand clearly by all.
- ✓ The Outdoor Advertising production costs are high and they cannot deliver sound and motion.
- ✓ The E-mail messages are in short life. Because, if messages are deleted they did not seen it.
- ✓ In Online Advertising involves more fraudulent activities and they need internet connection.

Opportunity:

- ✓ Nowadays media gives a big opportunity for Youngers, i.e, they are work perfectly and speedily.
- ✓ Many colleges have a better course about study of media, i.e., Bachelor of Visual Communication.
- ✓ Many persons have taken an opportunity to study viscom and work into the media.
- ✓ And media reporter's salary is too better compared to another field.
- ✓ In film Industry many opportunities are to act as best role and give better salary in media.

Threats:

- ✓ Some Medias create rumours against public.
- ✓ Sometimes Medias are used in negative way.

Internet's Role in Media:

Internet plays an important role in media. All information is updated under the www (World Wide Web) 24 hours a day through the media. News is telecasted through the internet. Now-a-days money is necessary for all and at the same time nearly 25% of the news is fake. Because, the media reporters aim are earning money through the media by the way of attracting public. Downloading items from online media sites. However, it should be noted that online editions often do not contain all printed and broadcast content.

Self-Concept and Social Media:

Since social media provides an easy way to receive feedback and communicate with all young adults attitudes of themselves can be affected by using social media networks. Due to digital technology, users can show considerable information about themselves and their friends. Many individuals use social network sites to feel popular, trying to add as many "friends" as possible so they appear to be more admired.

Media Analysis:

Media content Analysis is the deconstruction of pieces of media with tendency towards either quantitative and qualitative research methods. Media is a ongoing field of research, many research studies show that mass media have significant impact and effects on public awareness, perceptions and sometimes behaviour such as buying decisions etc.,

Quantitative media content analysis should be conducted in accordance with 'the scientific method'. Quantitative research methods within Media Content analysis point to a far more structured and consequently restricted form of gathering information from clips of media.

Qualitative content analysis can, to some extent, be incorporated within or conducted simultaneously with quantitative content analysis. Qualitative research methods involving a viewing of the clip and then unstructured open discussions and debate on the themes and effect on the clip.

Liberty of Media:

Nowadays, the prevention of ideas and expressing ideas are contrary to the pluralistic concept in modern democracies and, especially, it is gradually getting impossible from the point of political authority. The core of liberty of press is the freedom of thought and speech. The notions that the liberty of expression and criticizing may destroy social values aren't on favour of democracy although they are within the limits of democratic criticism.

There is a continuous relationship and interaction between the rulers having the power and the ruled ones. The public emerges during the process of this mutual relationships and interactions. The governments

should enable public getting information from numerous sources along with different and free comments and news.

The media is a tool which contributes to the declaration, announcement and spread of the opinions of various groups in the society through reflecting the opinion within itself and those belonging to the external environments; thus, provides an interaction between the rulers and ruled ones (Girgin, 2001, 144-145).

Conclusion:

Facebook and Twitter have emerged as the most popular websites and have continued to grow in popularity. These websites create new ways of communication with friends and family and also influence individual's self-concept. This study makes an important contribution in understanding college students' use of social media its effect to communication and self-concept.

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